

28th International Symposium on Analytical and Environmental Problems

PROCEEDINGS OF THE
28th International Symposium
on Analytical and Environmental Problems

Szeged, Hungary
November 14-15, 2022

University of Szeged

Edited by:

Tünde Alapi

Róbert Berkecz

István Ilisz

Publisher:

University of Szeged, H-6720 Szeged, Dugonics tér 13,
Hungary

ISBN 978-963-306-904-2

2022.

Szeged, Hungary

The 28th International Symposium on Analytical and Environmental Problems

Organized by:

SZAB Kémiai Szakbizottság Analitikai és Környezetvédelmi Munkabizottsága

Supporting Organizations

*Institute of Pharmaceutical Analysis, University of Szeged
Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Szeged*

Symposium Chairman:

István Ilisz, DSc

Honorary Chairman:

Zoltán Galbács, PhD

Organizing Committee:

István Ilisz, DSc

professor of chemistry

University of Szeged, Institute of Pharmaceutical Analysis

Tünde Alapi, PhD

assistant professor

University of Szeged, Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry

Róbert Berkecz, PhD

associate professor

University of Szeged, Institute of Pharmaceutical Analysis

Scientific Committee:

István Ilisz, DSc

Tünde Alapi, PhD

Róbert Berkecz, PhD

Daniela Sojic Merkulov, PhD

full professor

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection

SMOKING HABITS, CADMIUM EXPOSURE AND VULNERABILITY TO CHEMICALS OF LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA MALE PATIENTS IN VOJVODINA

Maja Milanović¹, Nataša Milošević¹, Danica Sazdanić Velikić^{1,2}, Jovana Drljača¹, Sanja Bijelović^{1,3}, Jan Sudji^{1,4}, Mirjana Ševo², Danijela Lukić³, Nataša Milić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

²Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for pulmonary oncology, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

³Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

⁴Institute of Occupational Health Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

email: maja.milanovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Introduction

The American Cancer Society estimates that each year, more people die of lung cancer than of colon, breast, and prostate cancers combined. It is evaluated that 87% lung cancers are non-small cell cases, out of which 52% are adenocarcinoma. During their lifetime, 1 in 15 men will be affected by lung cancer and the risk for the smokers is higher.

Experimental

In this research 28 male patients (39-77 years old) with inoperable IIIB and IV stadium of adenocarcinoma, diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Serbia were enrolled. The patients were asked to fulfil questionnaire regarding their exposure to chemicals during lifetime and their smoking habits. The presence of cadmium (Cd) was determined by ICP-MS in their morning urine samples.

Results and discussion

More than one third of the included patients, 35.71% (10/28) had been exposed to various chemicals during their education or in their free time, while 32.14% (9/28) have been exposed to chemicals professionally. The list of chemicals includes ammonia, mineral acids, pesticides, petroleum products, paints, varnishes, glues and organic solvents. Only 2 of them have not been smoking during their lifetime, while 92.86% (26/28) reported that have been or had been heavy cigarette smokers who had started to smoke on average at the age of 19.6 years. As ex-smokers were registered 57.14% (16/28) patients who had been smoking on average for 38 years 25.83 cigarettes a day. Active smokers who were included in this study 35.71% (10/28), smoke on average 29.17 cigarettes daily. Cd was detected in 53.57% (15/28) of total urine samples, 62.50% (10/16) of ex-smokers versus 40.00% (4/10) active smokers.

Conclusion

In this study for the first time, the exposure to chemicals and smoking habits among lung adenocarcinoma male patients in Western Balkan Region are reported.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia [grant number 142-451-2675/2021-01].